

Organizational Ambidexterity as a Mediating Variable between Psychological Capital and Strategic Success: An Applied Study

Author Details:

Prof. Dr. Wageeh A. Nafei-University of Sadat City, Menoufia, Egypt

Abstract

The overall objective of the study is to identify the role of Organizational Ambidexterity (OA) as a mediating variable in the relationship between Psychological Capital (PsyCap) and Strategic Success (SS). The research community is composed of all employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt. Due to the time and cost constraints, the researcher adopted the sampling method to collect the necessary data for the study. The appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses.

The research discovered a number of results, the most important of which: (1) findings support the view that the dimensions of PsyCap (hope, optimism, resilience, and self-efficacy) were positively related to OA (optimization of opportunities and Search for New opportunities). The results are consistent with research conducted by Erkutlu, 2013; Gooty et al., 2009; Luthans & Youssef, 2007; and Avey et al., 2006, (2) The results support the view that PsyCap is positively related to SS (limited strategy, effective implementation, motivational culture, horizontal organization, transformational leadership, continuous innovation). The results are consistent with research conducted by Quisenberry, 2015; Nafei, 2015; Paek et al., 2015; Avey et al., 2014; Abdelwahab, 2013; Avey, et al., 2010, and Gooty et al, 2009, (3) The results support the view that OA is positively related to SS. The results are consistent with research conducted by Tempelaar, 2010; Cao et al., 2010; Jansen et al., 2009; Han et al, 2001; and Wei et al., 2014, (4) There is a positive effect of OA as a mediating variable in explaining the effect of PsyCap on SS; that is, OA plays the mediating role in the relationship between PsyCap and SS. There is an impact on PsyCap on SS through OA. The results are consistent with research conducted by Jurksiene & Pundziene, 2016; Chang & Hughes, 2012; Bouzari & Karatepe, 2017; Peng et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2012, and Zhao & Zhang 2010.

The study referred to a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: (1) managers should be careful in assigning relatively stressful tasks to those who are low on PsyCap as these individuals are more likely to report job stress, (2) managers should pay attention to building and strengthening the PsyCap of their workers, (3) managers can enhance the PsyCap in one's organization to improve performance and competitive advantage, (4) managers can invest in PsyCap through encouraging learning among employees, (5) managers should take measures to increase employees' identification with their organization, such as striving for a higher organizational purpose, (7) the need to focus on the four dimensions of PsyCap and use them to increase OA and SS, (8) the need to train managers on how to develop the four dimensions of PsyCap through training courses targeting the spread of the spirit of hope and optimism among managers, and equipping them with skills to deal with different situations in order to ensure the achievement of positive feedback in the work environment, and (9) Teaching hospitals can increase the level of PsyCap by using short training sessions of one to three-hour micro interventions in which they measure PsyCap before and after the interventions.

Keywords: *Organizational Ambidexterity, Psychological Capital, Strategic Success*

1. Introduction

Psychological Capital (PsyCap) has received a great deal of attention from both academics and practitioners, which has been linked to staff attitudes and behaviors and performance at different levels of analysis (Newman et al., 2014).

The term psychological capital appeared in the late 1990s. It was mentioned by psychologist Martin Seligman whose aim was to focus on the positive qualities of the individual. The modern positive psychology movement has emerged since its official presentation at the American Psychological Association Conference in 1998s. A wide variety of positive activities geared towards social and human sciences emerged on happiness and excellence. One of the main aims of this science is to enhance individual self-efficacy through how to

exploit the strengths of individuals working in the organization rather than focusing on their weaknesses and shortcomings (Peterson et al., 2011).

Organizational Ambidexterity (OA) has its roots in 1976, a Latin word. A number of studies have confirmed that successful organizations seek new opportunities, be able to invest their current resources and uncover new possibilities (Siadat & Chaharmahali, 2010).

OA means an organization's ability to design structures that contribute to the application of innovation phases. OA is linked to exploitation and exploration activity. There is a fundamental difference between them, where exploitation activity is linked to processes such as optimization, efficiency, selection, and implementation. Exploration activity is associated with processes such as research, variation, and experimentation (Simsek, 2009).

OA is the ability to capitalize on existing competencies and explore new opportunities (Popadić et al., 2015).

OA is the ability of an organization to allocate resources for success in both exploration and exploitation. (Yigit, 2013)

The idea of OA is based on the fact that the requirements imposed by the environment may be incompatible, so that the most successful organizations can reconcile them and thus enhance competitiveness (Gibson & Birkinshaw, 2004).

The concept of Strategic Success (SS) is a modern term within the literature of management thought, where the literature of organizational theory focused on one of the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness, and with the passage of time and with the development of management thought literature no longer focus on the efficiency of the organization alone to judge its success, as organizations began to realize the importance of success strategic (Simon et al., 2011).

SS is the ability of the organization to formulate a good strategy that allows it to achieve its long-term goals that are consistent with the mission and vision of the organization, as well as a good and effective implementation of that strategy (David, 2009).

Today's organizations are often forced to change their strategic direction quickly to remain competitive. Fast technological developments, volatile consumer demand, and unpredictable market forces are catalysts for organizations wishing to be more successful (Eisenberg et al., 2015).

In light of the above, the present study seeks through the investigation and analysis to identify the role of OA as a mediating variable between PsyCap and SS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Psychological Capital

2.1.1. Psychological Capital Concept

PsyCap has been dealt with in a variety of businesses, but it extends beyond human and social capital "Instead of the philosophy "What do you know?" Or" Who do you know?". PsyCap has been neglected by academics and business practitioners, although it is an important part of human capital (what do I know?) and social capital (who do I know?) (Luthans et al., 2004).

PsyCap is an individual's positive, scalable mental state characterized by confidence (self-efficacy) to make the necessary efforts to succeed in challenging tasks, to create positive characteristic (optimism) about success now and in the future, to persevere towards achieving goals and when necessary reorienting paths (Hope) to succeed in achieving goals, and the ability to rebound (resilience) to succeed when exposed to problems and tribulations (Avey, 2014).

PsyCap is the generation of information that has the potential to be applied in education, to create an appropriate organization that meets the requirements of the work as well as information on leadership skills to create the necessary change when individuals achieve prosperity and achieve unique potential in the organization (Corner, 2015).

PsyCap is the positive psychic ability of an individual that is built along the lines of hope, trust, resilience, and optimism (Poon, 2013).

PsyCap is a set of personality traits that contribute to an individual's productivity, and represents a set of positive personal resources that enable individuals to achieve productivity and success in various aspects of life (Gohel, 2012)..

PsyCap is a positive psychological state developed for the individual described through (1) the individual's confidence to make the necessary efforts to achieve success in the performance of challenging tasks, (2) individuals make distinctive positive contributions to current and future success, (3) the individual strives to achieve the goals in order to achieve the desired success, and (4) the ability of the individual to endure when facing various problems and obstacles towards the pursuit of goals (Luthans et al., 2007).

2.1.2. Psychological Capital Dimensions

There are four dimensions of PsyCap. They are self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience. These dimensions have proven valid across different cultures (Han et al., 2012). They can be explained as follows:

1. Self-Efficacy: It is the interaction of individuals working in the organization and expressing their opinions freely without fear or doubt (Lima, 2015). Self-efficacy is the confidence of individuals in their ability to mobilize their motivation, their knowledge resources, and take the necessary actions to successfully accomplish their mandated work within the organization under certain environmental conditions (Luthans & Youssef, 2017; Larson & Luthans, 2006). It is the perception or belief of an individual that he or she can successfully perform a particular task (Bandura, 2012). Self-efficacy is the ability to be confident and successful, and to transfer those abilities in a stimulating way to achieve the goal (Chen & Lim, 2012). It is the belief in one's own abilities and skills and their success, regardless of their surroundings (Avey et al., 2010). Self-efficacy is an individual's confidence to make the necessary efforts to succeed in challenging tasks (Luthans et al., 2007).

2. Optimism: It reflects a person's view of events; successful or failed. A person who is optimistic views events successfully and the reason for this success is due to internal factors, and the pessimistic person is the cause of success due to temporary external factors (Brockorny, 2015).

Optimism is divided into realistic optimism and unrealistic optimism. Realistic optimism is the result of maintaining a positive view of things in the future, focusing on the positive aspects stemming from the individual's experience, leaving the events of the past, focusing more on the present and looking for opportunities in the future to seize them. Unrealistic optimism reflects the existence of some information that one does not want to retain through certain beliefs, and this leads to the failure to achieve the goals to be achieved (Corner, 2015).

Optimism is the degree to which individuals have an outcome of expectations of positive outcomes, so that they believe that good things will happen to them in relation to their work (Schmitt et al., 2013).

Optimistic individuals are distinctive that they have positive expectations about the outcomes of specific events, believing in their ability to succeed in several areas, and persistence and continuing to achieve that success, while when they fail they face that failure through many unlimited contributions (Seligman, 2002). An optimist recognizes the ordeal as a temporary setback and that opportunities remain (Luthans, 2005; Youssef & Luthans, 2007).

Optimism refers to creating the positive characteristic and expectations of the best for present and future success (Luthans et al., 2007).

3. Hope: It is to possess the willpower and paths necessary to achieve the desired goals. It is also the belief of the individual that he can find alternative paths to the desired goals and become a catalyst for the use of these paths (Luthans & Youssef, 2017).

Hope is the need to persevere in achieving goals and redirecting paths to reach high efficiency. This is the basis of the difference between it and the traditional definition of hope, that is, the traditional definition is to wish for something and one might be disappointed if it is not achieved without retrying (Brockorny, 2015).

Hope is a formation of successful will associated with a specific plan, which is aimed at the successful completion of some desired tasks or outputs. The hope is to realize the individual's ability to derive pathways that lead to the desired goals, and to motivate the individual through the power and energy of goal-oriented thinking to use these pathways (Avey, 2014).

Hope is the ability to find ways and means to reach the goals that a person aspires to have with positive psychic possibilities. If these methods do not work, he thinks in other ways to reach and persist in the goals to be reached (Javidan & Walker, 2013).

Hope includes three main directions: strength, path, and purpose. The direction of force is the will to achieve the desired goal, and it serves as a catalyst to reach that goal. The pathway is the alternative to be pursued in the pursuit of the goal, which is determined by the planning of the situation and the prediction of the obstacles in the way of the goal as a proactive measure to achieve the desired goal (Avey, 2014).

Hope refers to persistence and pursuit of goals, and redirecting paths towards those goals where necessary in order to succeed (Luthans et al., 2007).

4. Resilience: It is an important element associated with improving the performance of the organization as a whole, as change generates high tension in the environment of the organization, so leaders need to pay attention to the element of resilience (Corner, 2015), and develop it in a way that achieves satisfaction and job commitment (Murray, 2014).

Resilience is the reaction and positive adaptation that an individual shows when experiencing problems and constraints (Masten & Reed, 2002).

Resilience is the positive psychic abilities to rebound or returning from obstacles, uncertainty, conflict, failure, and even severe positive changes and progress achieved by an individual, and increased responsibilities upon him (Luthans, 2002).

Resilience is a positive response not only to adverse events but also to positive events that can cause adverse reactions on the part of the individual, as well as in the form of pressures on the individual (Norman, 2006).

The organization can achieve resilience by taking advantage of mistakes and considering them as lessons that generate an opportunity for the organization to develop itself and seize those opportunities through learning, growth and development (Bockorny, 2015).

Whenever the organization is flexible, its leaders will also be flexible. Resilience can be developed through three main strategies (1) an asset-focused strategy, which means increasing resilience by building individual assets and increasing the likelihood of success. (2) a strategy of focusing on risk means trying to reduce failure by minimizing risk factors, and (3) a strategy of focusing on the process and trying to build effective mechanisms so that workers can deploy their assets (Poon, 2013).

Resilience refers to endurance and a return to the appropriate state in the event of an individual's problems and adversity in pursuit of goals (Luthans et al., 2007).

2.2. Organizational Ambidexterity

2.2.1. Organizational Ambidexterity Concept

OA can be viewed through three perspectives. They are (1) the interval between exploitation and exploration activities, where the organization exploits at one time and explores at another, (2) the structural separation between exploitation and exploration, where the organization exploits in certain sections, and explores in other sections, (3) specialization between companies, where one company exploits, and another explores (Prieto & Santan, 2012).

OA is the link between exploring and exploiting opportunities for all individuals and sub-units of the organization (Adler & Heckscher, 2011).

OA is the ability of the organization to link the exploration and exploitation of opportunities (Bodwell, 2011).

OA is the organizational capacity to exploit available competencies, as well as to explore new opportunities (Danzinger & Dumbach, 2011).

OA is the ability to use skills, achieve innovations and strive to distinguish an organization from competing organizations. This is done through the exploitation of available resources and the pursuit of skills that achieve competitive excellence focused on new opportunities (Cao, et al. 2010).

OA is the ability of an organization to capitalize on existing knowledge and explore new knowledge (Shoo, 2010).

OA is the organization's ability to optimize opportunities and seek new opportunities (Walrave et al, 2010).

OA can be embodied at the level of team operations through the ability of organization staff to find creative solutions to problems in the light of a shared vision and mutual trust (Tempelaar, 2010).

OA is the ability of an organization to perform various actions such as stabilization, the search for new resources, efficiency, flexibility, exploration, exploitation, harmonization, adaptation and overall innovation, progressive innovation, growth strategy, and profit strategy. In other words, OA is the organization's pursuit of interdependence among all activities. It also seeks to achieve adaptation by restructuring its activities in a manner that achieves competitive excellence. In other words, all activities are interconnected, and adaptation means restructuring activities quickly to meet changes in the environment (Simsek, 2009).

OA is an integrated concept that points to a twin approach to exploration and exploitation (Cao & et al., 2010).

OA is the ability of the organization to achieve both exploitation and exploration, by excelling in existing opportunities to achieve gradual innovation that is concerned with modifying an existing product, and exploring new opportunities to foster innovation that is concerned with product change (Andriopoulos & Lewis, 2009).

OA is the ability of an organization to achieve competition in two directions: to exploit available resources, and to discover new resources or business that can achieve excellence from competing organizations (Taylor & Helfat, 2009).

OA can be seen by (1) separating exploitation and exploration activities, (2) structural separation between exploitation and exploration, and (3) specialization between organizations (Tran, 2008).

OA is the organization's pursuit of innovation and short-term operational objectives while maintaining long-term performance rates (Im & Rai, 2008).

OA is the ability of an organization to operate efficiently and effectively in managing its current business at the same time as it can adapt to changes in the internal and external environment of the organization (Raisch & Birkinshaw, 2008).

OA is the ability of an organization to balance the exploitation of existing possibilities and explore new opportunities (He & Wong, 2004).

OA is the extent to which an organization can achieve adaptation to all variables that occur in the environment and strive to improve long-term performance levels (Gibson & Birkinshaw, 2004).

2.2.2. Organizational Ambidexterity Dimensions

Researchers differed on the dimensions of OA according to the different philosophies of the providers and the objectives they seek to achieve. Two fundamental dimensions of OA have been the highest agreement among researchers. In other words, there are two dimensions of OA. They are (1) exploitation of existing capabilities and satisfying the needs of existing customers and markets by improving existing products and processes, (2) exploration refers to the search for new possibilities and opportunities, new customers and new markets through a radical change based on the introduction of new products and processes in the organization. The present study relied on two main dimensions (He & Wong, 2004; Gibson & Birkinshaw, 2004; Jansen 2005; Lubatkin et al., 2006; Bierly & Daly, 2007; Jansen et al., 2008; Shoo, 2010):

1. **Optimization of opportunities:** It refers to an organization's ability to improve activities to create value in the short term, to meet the needs of existing customers in the market, to seek to expand existing knowledge and skills, as well as to expand existing products or services, while increasing existing distribution channels.
2. **Search for new opportunities:** It refers to the need for the organization to mobilize its efforts to obtain new opportunities, where the organization is working to determine the future demands of existing customers, as well as anticipating changes in the type of applications, and the need for the organization to seek new opportunities. The organization can seize opportunities by adopting new ways of delivering goods and services, undertaking competitive actions to confront other organizations and how to improve the competitive position and respond to market changes.

Exploration and exploitation are competing approaches for a number of reasons, the most important of which are: (1) exploration and exploitation strategies often compete for the limited resources of the organization; (2) exploitation strategies reduce the exploration of the organization, while exploration strategies reduce the exploitation of the organization's resources, (3) the organization faces a major problem of how to balance the exploration and exploitation activities, where exploitation activities ensure the present survival, and exploration activities ensure future survival (Kyriakopoulos & Moorman, 2004).

In light of the above, exploration is concerned with exploring new possibilities and opportunities, searching for new customers and entering new markets, increasing the company's ability to adapt quickly and appropriately to the fundamental changes that occur in the market, while exploiting the current possibilities and satisfy the needs of existing customers and current markets (Patel et al., 2013).

2.3. Strategic Success

2.3.1. Strategic Success Concept

There are several definitions of SS where the success of an organization depends to a large extent on its investment of mental capacity in terms of transferring, learning and implementing new knowledge (Dzinkowski, 2000).

SS is the ability of the organization to create value for its shareholders both within and outside the organization (Waldron & Antonio, 2008).

SS is the success in the strategic formulation of the organization and work to implement and follow-up (Johnson & Scholes, 2002).

2.3.2. Strategic Success Dimensions

It is worth noting that according to (Ghurchiau, et al., 2010), the dimensions of SS are as follows:

1. **Survival:** it is what organizations seek to achieve. Companies will end when they are incompatible with changes in their surroundings.
2. **Adaptation:** the organization is able to adapt quickly to the work environment and events that are supposed to be able to manage change and deal with and adapt to it and improve its ability to survive and grow in the surrounding environment.
3. **Growth:** it is the aspects that the company needs to take to help it develop, grow and thrive though changes are increasingly taking place in the organization environment.

The first to point to the need to rely on a balanced scorecard to measure the organization's strategic success is (Kaplan & Norton, 2005). This is through four key criteria: learning and growth, internal processes, stakeholders and financial performance. It should be noted that there are several other dimensions that can be relied upon to measure the strategic success of the organization, and these dimensions are as follows (Simon et al., 2011):

1. **Limited Strategy:** successful organizations are interested in formulating clear, specific strategies, while companies that are unable to survive and face challenges are failing to formulate a strategy to scale up.

2. **Effective implementation:** the organization is concerned with the effective implementation of its strategy. The organization is keen to satisfy its customers, while we find failed companies in a state of incapacity and unable to implement its strategy.
3. **Motivational culture:** successful companies are characterized by a positive culture that motivates work and development, while failed companies do not have a direction through which to build a culture of motivation, through which they can activate the work and workers.
4. **Horizontal organization:** decentralization is the secret of the success of organizations to enable their managers to make decisions and participate in shaping the future of the organization, while insisting organizations failing to take central management system, which impedes their progress and the effectiveness of their employees.
5. **Transformational leadership:** the ability of the leader to communicate the mission and vision of the future clearly to the followers and motivate them through the practice of high ethical behaviors to build trust and respect between the parties to achieve the goals of the organization.
6. **Continuous innovations:** the ability to compete and reach products and customers and new markets faster and better than its competitors as it is a factor of continuity and survival of enterprises.

3. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram shows that there is one independent variable of PsyCap. There is one dependent variable of SS. There is one mediating variable of OA.

Figure (1): Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The research framework suggests that OA plays a significant role in the relationship between PsyCap and SS.

The research framework suggests that OA plays a significant role in the relationship between PsyCap and SS.

PsyCap as measured consists of self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience (Luthans et al., 2007).

OA is measured in terms of optimization of opportunities and search for new opportunities (Jansen 2005).

SS is measured in terms of limited strategy, effective implementation, motivational culture, horizontal organization, transformational leadership, continuous innovation (Simon et al., 2011; Joyce et al., 2004).

4. Research Questions

The issue of PsyCap is of interest to a number of researchers in the field of management, as it plays an important role in improving the behavior of employees (Goody et al, 2009). Employee attitudes are represented

in job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Nafei, 2015). PsyCap helps individuals adapt to the complexities of a changing work environment. There are clear advantages of PsyCap in contemporary organizational research (Avey, et al., 2010).

Many researchers have begun to use OA as an integral part of building the hallmark of organizations in terms of exploration and investment (Cao et al., 2010).

Exploration and investment activities are learning activities, which require the leaders of organizations to pay attention to the distribution of their resources. These activities create diversity to find new ways of dealing with renewable technologies, which requires considerable flexibility in regulatory procedures (Batta, 2006; Wulf et al., 2010).

To achieve SS, we find that it is linked to a distinct kind of mental capabilities needed by the manager or strategic leader that allows him to think comprehensively about the future of the organization and the scarcity of information. This is in addition to the need to meet many requirements of customer satisfaction, maintaining market share and the possibility of increasing, and satisfaction of workers (Madsen & Desai, 2010).

SS is a system that helps decision-making by observing and analyzing the practical environment and technological technology. In addition to tracking current and future economic impacts to capture opportunities and threats based on strategic information. It is defined as the ability of the organization to achieve long-term success associated with achieving strategic objectives and achieving higher performance levels than competitors (McDowell, 2010).

As human resources are increasingly recognized as a competitive advantage, terms such as human capital, social capital. They have been dealt with both in theory and in practice. However, PsyCap has been ignored by academics and practitioners that focus on the personal strengths of individuals (Luthans et al., 2004).

The researcher conducted a pilot study aimed at obtaining exploratory data of PsyCap, the level of OA, and the SS of the different categories of workers in the Egyptian Teaching hospitals. This is in addition to helping the researcher to identify the research problem and to reach a precise formulation of the research hypotheses.

In the pilot study, secondary data were collected on the variables of the study, namely PsyCap, OA and SS. This is in addition to an interview with (30) employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt to identify the dimensions of PsyCap, OA and SS.

In addition to the personal observation of the researcher during the visit to the Teaching hospitals in Egypt in the pilot study, the researcher has reached a set of preliminary results, namely (1) not participating in setting goals related to the field of work, which reflects negatively on the level of hope of employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt, (2) lack of awareness of the vocabulary of the sample of the level of PsyCap, and the inability to determine the level of OA. Also, there is the inability to know the level of SS. This is in addition to the ambiguity of the relationship between PsyCap, OA and SS, (3) the scarcity of the administrative leaders to hold scientific seminars where the terms of hope, optimism, indulgence and dedication are the focus of the talk, and (4) the pessimistic view of the employees and the weakness of the search for alternative solutions to the problems and obstacles facing the employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Although there have been numerous studies on PsyCap, OA and SS alone, the researcher did not find in the Arab environment a study that tried to link the variables of the field of application of the study.

In light of the review of previous studies that dealt with the subject of the study, and the pilot study carried out by the researcher, the research problem can be mainly reflected in the low level of PsyCap dimensions of the staff in Teaching hospitals. This is reflected negatively on the level of OA on the one hand, and SS on the other. More specifically, this study seeks through the investigation and analysis to answer the following questions:

Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between PsyCap and OA at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?

Q2: What is the extent of the relationship between PsyCap and SS at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?

Q3: What is the nature of the relationship between OA and SS at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?

Q4: What is the role of OA as a mediating variable between PsyCap and SS at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?

5. Research Hypotheses

The results of many previous studies confirm the relationship between PsyCap and some other variables, not including OA, where one of the studies is concerned with the analysis of the relationship between PsyCap and organizational commitment. The results of this study indicated that there is a positive relationship between hope as one of the dimensions of PsyCap and organizational commitment. There is an inverse relationship between resilience as one of the dimensions of PsyCap and organizational commitment, whereas optimism, self-efficacy and organizational commitment are not. The results also indicated that there is a significant correlation between one of the dimensions of PsyCap and emotional commitment as one of the dimensions of organizational commitment (Erkutlu, 2013).

Another study aimed at testing the transformational leadership model as one of the determinants of positive PsyCap. It represents the individual catalyst towards achieving goals. The results of this study confirmed that there is a relationship between subordinates' perception of transformational leadership and PsyCap (Gooty et al., 2009).

Another study focused on determining the impact of PsyCap on work-related outcomes. The results indicated that positive psychological resources contribute significantly to positive results (Luthans & Youssef, 2007).

Another study emphasized the relationship between PsyCap and intentional and unintentional absence, as well as job satisfaction and organizational commitment. These studies have found that the interaction between PsyCap and the rate of absence of employees is due to the actual association between work stress and the psychological aspects of workers. The reactions of workers in the workplace vary according to their level of PsyCap (Avey et al., 2006).

Accordingly, the first hypothesis of the study can be formulated in the form of imposition of nothingness as follows:

First hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between PsyCap and OA at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

The results of several previous studies confirm the relationship between PsyCap and some other variables, not including SS. This study emphasized that PsyCap contributes to increasing creativity, cooperation among workers, the stability of employees, stimulating motivation, developing work productivity, happiness at work, showing healthy attitudes towards work and increasing efficiency and effectiveness in work. (Quisenberry, 2015).

Another study aimed at identifying the nature of the relationship between PsyCap and job attitudes. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between PsyCap and both job satisfaction and organizational commitment. PsyCap contributes to the improvement of the job satisfaction of employees and increases the degree of commitment on the other hand (Nafei, 2015).

Another study focused on the nature of the relationship between PsyCap and work engagement. The study indicated that the higher the level of PsyCap of employees, the higher their association with work (Paek et al., 2015).

Another study focused on the nature of the relationship between PsyCap and the abandonment of work. This study confirmed that PsyCap contributes significantly to reducing the intention to leave work and the search for a job (Avey et al., 2014).

Another study confirmed that attention to PsyCap contributes significantly to reducing undesirable organizational behaviors such as the intention to leave work, anti-productive workplace behaviors, and withdrawal from the job, where PsyCap increases the desire of workers to stay in the organization, and makes them not think in her abandonment (Abdelwahab, 2013).

Another study aimed to test the impact of PsyCap on the desired organizational outputs. The study found that positive PsyCap contributes significantly to increase creativity and decrease the rate of absenteeism, increase performance rates, and increase organizational loyalty (Avey, et al., 2010).

Another study focused on the nature of the relationship between PsyCap and some other variables such as organizational citizenship behavior. The results of this study indicated that there is a positive relationship between PsyCap and organizational citizenship behavior (Gooty et al, 2009).

Accordingly, the second hypothesis of the study can be formulated in the form of imposition of nothingness as follows:

Second hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between PsyCap and SS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

There have been many previous studies on the relationship between OA and some other variables, not including SS. A study indicated that the characteristics of leadership and organizational structure contribute to the emergence of OA. The study confirmed the existence of a positive relationship between the characteristics of leadership and organizational structure and the balance between the dimensions of OA (exploration and exploitation). The study found that OA plays the mediating role between organizational structure, leadership characteristics and organizational performance (Chang & Hughes, 2012).

Another study aimed to know the relationship between emergency rewards and social integration of the senior management team and OA. The study found a positive relationship between the social integration of the senior management team and OA, while there was no relationship between emergency rewards and OA (Tempelaar, 2010).

While another study examined the impact of each executive manager and the support of top management on OA. The study found a positive impact on the executive manager and senior management support on OA and the formation of an organizational structure that is skill-oriented (Cao et al., 2010).

Another study emphasized the relationship between OA and some variables such as cooperation, administrative communication, central decision-making, and the effectiveness of the team. The study pointed out that there is an inverse relationship between organizational excellence and central decision-making (Jansen et al., 2009).

Another study emphasized the relationship between OA and some variables such as cooperation, administrative communication, central decision-making, and the effectiveness of the team. The study concluded that there is a positive correlation between OA and cooperation, administrative communication, team effectiveness and OA. The study pointed out that there is an inverse relationship between OA and central decision-making (Jansen et al., 2009).

Another study found a positive relationship between OA and performance, especially in technology-oriented companies. The study also found that high levels of technology encourage OA from low levels (Han et al, 2001).

Another study examined the impact of exploration and exploitation on the performance of the organization by comparing organizations using pioneering and defensive strategies. The study found a positive correlation between exploitation and the performance of the organization, while there is a relationship between exploration and the performance of the organization (Wei et al., 2014).

Accordingly, the third hypothesis of the study can be formulated in the form of imposition of nothingness as follows:

The third hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship between OA and SS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Several previous studies have addressed OA as a mediating variable, not including PsyCap and SS either directly or indirectly. A study (Jurksiene & Pundziene, 2016) aimed to illustrate the role of OA as a mediating variable in the relationship between dynamic capabilities and competitive advantage. The study found that dynamic capabilities and OA are linked to competitive advantage, and OA plays a mediating role in the relationship between dynamic capabilities and competitive advantage.

The Chang & Hughes (2012) study also highlighted the role of OA as a mediating variable between organizational structure, leadership characteristics and the performance of organizations. The study confirmed

that there is a positive relationship between the characteristics of leadership and organizational structure and the balance between the dimensions of OA (exploration and exploitation).

However, a study (Bouzari & Karatepe, 2017) emphasized the importance of the role of PsyCap as a mediating variable in influencing the intention of delays among employees, the intention to stay with the organization, the ingenuity of services and sales, and organizational citizenship behaviors.

A study (Peng et al., 2013) indicated that organizational commitment partly mediates the relationship between PsyCap and job burnout.

The study (Wang et al., 2012) found that PsyCap plays a mediating role between the conflict between work and family, and professional competence.

The study (Zhao & Zhang 2010) focused on the emphasis on PsyCap as a mediating variable between the job stress and job burnout. The study showed that PsyCap is positively associated with the dimensions of job burnout, in addition to that it affects the relationship between job stress and job burnout.

Accordingly, the fourth hypothesis of the study can be formulated in the form of imposition of nothingness as follows:

The fourth hypothesis: There is no statistically significant effect of OA as a mediating variable between PsyCap and SS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

6. Research Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. This sector includes nine Hospitals. They are Ahmed Maher, El-Matrya, El-Galaa, El-Sahel, Benha, Shebin El-Kom, Damanhour, Sohag and Aswan. The population of this study includes 5000 employees. The random sampling was used for collecting the primary data as it was difficult to get all items of the research population, because of time limitations. The stratified random sample was used while selecting items from the different categories of employees. The following equation determines the sampling size (Daniel, 1999):

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

Accordingly, the sample size has become 357 employees at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. Proportionality with the number of employees in the research population is proved in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size on the Population

Job Category	Number	Percentage	Size of Sample
Physicians	2000	40%	357 X 40% = 143
Nurses	3000	60%	357 X 60% = 214
Total	5000	100%	357 X 100% = 357

Source: Personnel Department at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt, 2018

By using the lists of employees at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt, a random choice of categories was attained. Table (2) illustrates the features of the sample units.

Table (2) Characteristics of Items of the Sample

Research Variables		Number	Percentage
1- Job Title	Physicians	135	45%
	Nurses	165	55%
	Total	300	100%
2- Sex	Male	130	43%
	Female	170	57%
	Total	300	100%
3- Marital Status	Single	100	33%
	Married	200	67%
	Total	300	100%
4- Age	Under 30	130	43%

	From 30 to 45	120	40%
	Above 45	50	17%
	Total	300	100%
5- Educational Level	University	200	67%
	Post Graduate	100	33%
	Total	300	100%
6- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	110	37%
	From 5 to 10	100	33%
	More than 10	90	30%
	Total	300	100%

7. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the significant role of OA in the relationship between PsyCap and SS. A survey research method was used to collect data in this study. The questionnaire included four questions, relating to PsyCap, OA, SS and biographical information of employees at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. Data collection took approximately two months. About 357 survey questionnaires were distributed. Multiple follow-ups yielded 300 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 84%.

8. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

The 24-item scale PsyCap section is based on Luthans, 2006. There were six items measuring hope, six items measuring optimism, six items measuring resilience, and six items measuring self-efficacy.

The 14-item scale OA section is based on Jansen, 2005. There were seven items measuring optimization of opportunities and seven items measuring Search for New opportunities.

The 28-item scale SS section is based on Simon et al., 2011; Joyce et al., 2004. There were six items measuring limited strategy, four items measuring effective implementation, four items measuring motivational culture, six items measuring horizontal organization, four items measuring transformational leadership, and four items measuring continuous innovation.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

9. Methods of Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach’s Alpha, (2) Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA), and (3) the statistical testing of hypotheses which includes F- test and T-test. They are found in SPSS.

Also, the researcher used the Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) to measure the direct and indirect effects of PsyCap on SS, as well as the measurement of the intermediate role of OA, through the indicators of conformity of alternative models on the one hand, and the model that achieves these indicators on the other hand.

9.1. Coding of Variables

The main variables, sub-variables, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3): Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

	Main Variables	Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	Psychological Capital	Hope	6	Luthans, 2006
		Optimism	6	
		Resilience	6	
		Self-efficacy	6	
	Total PsyCap		24	
Quoting Variable	Organizational	Optimization of Opportunities	7	Jansen 2005

	Ambidexterity	Search for New Opportunities	7	
Total OA			14	
Dependent Variable	Strategic Success	Limited Strategy	6	Simon et al., 2011; Joyce et al., 2004
		Effective Implementation	4	
		Motivational Culture	4	
		Horizontal Organization	6	
		Transformational Leadership	4	
		Continuous Innovation	4	
Total SS			28	

9.2. Descriptive Analysis

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, descriptive statistics were performed to find out means and standard deviations of PsyCap, OA, and SS.

Table (4) lists the mean and standard deviation among variables. The mean of each variable is more than 3, and this result indicates that the study subjects in general have a higher level of PsyCap, OA and SS. The different facets of PsyCap (hope, optimism, resilience and self-efficacy) are examined. Most respondents identified the presence of self-efficacy (M=3.81, SD=1.16). This was followed by resilience (M=3.73, SD=1.16), hope (M=3.56, SD=1.17), and optimism (M=3.52, SD=1.17).

Table (4) shows the mean and standard deviations of PsyCap, OA, and SS

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
PsyCap	Hope	3.560	1.174
	Optimism	3.529	1.178
	Resilience	3.738	1.168
	Self-Efficacy	3.812	1.166
	Total Measurement	3.660	0.978
OA	Optimization of Opportunities	3.511	0.999
	Search for New Opportunities	3.445	1.078
	Total Measurement	3.478	1.013
SS	Limited Strategy	3.755	1.090
	Effective Implementation	3.640	1.234
	Motivational Culture	3.501	1.020
	Horizontal Organization	3.332	1.040
	Transformational Leadership	3.735	1.167
	Continuos Innovation	3.769	1.151
	Total Measurement	3.611	0.906

The different facets of OA (optimization of opportunities and search for new opportunities) are examined. Most respondents identified the presence of optimization of opportunities (M=3.51, SD=0.999). This was followed by a search for new opportunities (M=3.44, SD=1.07).

The different facets of SS (limited strategy, effective implementation, motivational culture, horizontal organization, transformational leadership, and continues innovation) are examined. Most respondents identified the presence of limited strategy (M=3.75, SD=1.09). This was followed by effective implementation (M=3.64, SD=1.23), motivational culture (M=3.50, SD=1.02), horizontal organization (M=3.33, SD=1.04), transformational leadership (M=3.73, SD=1.16), and continues innovation (M=3.76, SD=1.15).

9.3. Evaluating Reliability

ACC was used to evaluate the degree of internal consistency among the contents of the scale under testing. Table (5) shows the results of the reliability test for each variable of PsyCap, OA, and SS.

ACC was decided to exclude variables that had a correlation coefficient of less than 0.30 when the acceptable limits of ACC range from 0.60 to 0.80, in accordance with levels of reliability analysis in social sciences (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach’s alpha test was conducted. Table (4) shows the reliability results for PsyCap, OA and SS. All items had alphas above 0.60 and were therefore excellent, according to Langdridge’s (2004) criteria.

The 24 items of PsyCap are reliable because the ACC is 0.966. The six items of hope scales are reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.949. The optimism, which consists of six items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.941. The six items related to resilience are reliable as ACC is 0.966. Furthermore, the self-efficacy, which consists of six items, is reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.947.

Table (5) Reliability of PsyCap, OA, and SS

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
PsyCap	Hope	6	0.949
	Optimism	6	0.941
	Resilience	6	0.966
	Self-Efficacy	6	0.947
	Total Measurement	24	0.966
OA	Optimization of Opportunities	7	0.883
	Search for New Opportunities	7	0.972
	Total Measurement	14	0.950
SS	Limited Strategy	6	0.910
	Effective Implementation	4	0.949
	Motivational Culture	4	0.812
	Horizontal Organization	6	0.882
	Transformational Leadership	4	0.925
	Continuos Innovation	4	0.914
	Total Measurement	28	0.960

The 14 items of OA because the ACC is 0.950. The optimization of opportunities, which consists of five items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.883 while the six items related to search for new opportunities is reliable as the ACC is 0.972.

The 28 items of SS are reliable because the ACC is 0.960. The six items of limited strategy scales are reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.910. The effective implementation, which consists of six items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.949. The six items related to motivational culture are reliable as ACC is 0.812. Furthermore, the horizontal organization, which consists of six items, is reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.882. The six items of transformational leadership scales are reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.925. The continues innovation, which consists of six items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.914.

9.4. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (6) Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix for all Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	PsyCap	OA	SS
Psychological Capital	3.660	0.978	1.000		
Organizational Ambidexterity	3.478	1.013	0.689**	1.000	
Strategic Success	3.611	0.906	0.881**	0.875**	1.000

Table (6) shows correlation coefficients between the research variables, and results indicate the presence of a significant correlation between variables (PsyCap, OA, and SS).

The level of PsyCap of employees is average (Mean=3.66; SD=0.978), while OA is higher (Mean=3.47; SD 1.01) which led to a high level of SS (Mean=3.61; SD 0.906).

Table (6) reveals the existence of a positive correlation between PsyCap and OA ($R=0.689$; $P < 0.01$), which means that the high level of PsyCap leads to higher OA. Also, the table shows that there is a positive correlation between PsyCap and SS ($R= 0.881$; $P < 0.01$), which means that the high level of PsyCap leads to higher SS. According to Table (6), there is a positive correlation between OA and SS ($R=0.875$; $P < 0.01$), which means that the high level of OA leads to higher SS.

9.5. The Correlation between PsyCap and OA

Table (7): Correlation Matrix among PsyCap and OA

Research Variables	1	2	3	4	5
Hope	1				
Optimism	0.921**	1			
Resilience	0.755**	0.723**	1		
Self-Efficacy	0.334**	0.322**	0.515**	1	
Organizational Ambidexterity	0.571**	0.524**	0.775**	0.432**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (7), the correlation between PsyCap (Hope) and OA is 0.571. For PsyCap (Optimism) and OA, the value is 0.524 whereas PsyCap (Resilience) and OA show a correlation value of 0.775. Also, the correlation between PsyCap (Self-Efficacy) and OA is 0.432. The overall correlation between PsyCap and OA is 0.698.

9.6. Psychological Capital and Organizational Ambidexterity

The relationship between PsyCap and OA is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no statistically significant relationship between PsyCap and OA at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.

Table (8) MRA Results for PsyCap and OA

The Variables of PsyCap	Beta	R	R ²
1. Hope	0.113	0.571	0.326
2. Optimism	0.161	0.524	0.274
3. Resilience	0.785**	0.775	0.600
4. Self-Efficacy	0.042	0.432	0.186
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.779	0.606
		113.652	4, 295
		3.31	0.000
* P < 0.05 ** P < 0.01			

As Table (8) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.779 demonstrating that the independent variables of PsyCap construe OA significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, independent variables of PsyCap can explain 60% of the total factors in OA level. Hence, 40% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.7. The Correlation between PsyCap and SS

Table (9): Correlation Matrix among PsyCap and SS

Research Variables	1	2	3	4	5
Hope	1				
Optimism	0.921**	1			
Resilience	0.755**	0.723**	1		
Self-Efficacy	0.334**	0.322**	0.515**	1	
Strategic Success	0.684**	0.677**	0.874**	0.707**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (9), the correlation between PsyCap (Hope) and SS is 0.684. For PsyCap (Optimism) and SS, the value is 0.677 whereas PsyCap (Resilience) and SS show a correlation value of 0.874. Also, the correlation between PsyCap (Self-Efficacy) and SS is 0.707. The overall correlation between PsyCap and SS is 0.881.

9.8. Psychological Capital and Strategic Success

The relationship between PsyCap and SS is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is: *There is no statistically significant relationship between PsyCap and SS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.*

Table (10) MRA Results for PsyCap and SS

The Variables of PsyCap	Beta	R	R ²
1. Hope	0.039	0.684	0.467
2. Optimism	0.162**	0.677	0.458
3. Resilience	0.602**	0.874	0.763
4. Self-Efficacy	0.357**	0.707	0.499
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.928	
		0.862	
		460.906	
		4, 295	
		3.31	
		0.000	
* P < .05 ** P < 0.01			

As Table (10) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.928 demonstrating that the independent variables of PsyCap construe SS significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, independent variables of PsyCap can explain 86% of the total factors in the SS level. Hence, 14% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.9. The Correlation between OA and SS

Table (11): Correlation Matrix among OA and SS

Research Variables	1	2	3
Optimization of Opportunities	1		
Search for New Opportunities	0.904**	1	
Organizational Ambidexterity	0.845**	0.861**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (11), the correlation between OA (Optimization of Opportunities) and SS is 0.845. For OA (Search for New Opportunities) and SS, the value is 0.861. The overall correlation between OA and SS is 0.875.

9.10. Organizational Ambidexterity and Strategic Success

The relationship between PsyCap and SS is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is: *There is no statistically significant relationship between OA and SS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.*

Table (12) MRA Results for OA and SS

The Variables of OA	Beta	R	R ²
1. Optimization of Opportunities	0.364	0.845	0.714
2. Search for New Opportunities	0.532	0.861	0.741
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.875	
		0.766	
		485.650	
		2, 297	
		4.60	
		0.000	
* P < .05 ** P < 0.01			

As Table (12) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.875 demonstrating that the independent variables of OA construe SS significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, independent variables of OA can explain 76% of the total factors in SS. Hence, 24% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.11. OA as a Mediating Variable of the Relationship between PsyCap and SS

The study of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable through the intermediate variable is an important subject in social studies. The researcher relied on Holmbeck (1997) to measure the role of OA as an intermediate variable in interpreting the impact of PsyCap on SS by testing the following model.

This model is based on the indirect effect of the independent variable (PsyCap) and the dependent variable (SS) through the intermediate variable (OA). The structural model of the partially mediated model can be illustrated in Figure (4). It is clear that there is an indirect influence between the PsyCap (the independent variable) on SS (the dependent variable) and the OA (the mediating variable).

Figure (2): The Structural Model of the Search Variables

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

The different indicators of the quality of the partial mediation model can be explained by the following table:

Table (13): Match Quality Indicators for the Direct Impact Model of Search Variables

Test the Quality of the Model	Test Value	Acceptance Condition ^(*)
X ² / Degree of freedom	2019.794	(X ² / df) < 5
P. value	0.000	P > 0.5
Goodness of fit Index (GFI)	0.842	GFI > 0.90
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI)	0.504	TLI > 0.9
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.609	CFI > 0.95
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.604	NFI > 0.90
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	0.610	IFI > 0.9

(*) Daire et al., 2008

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of AMOS, V.23, 2015

In light of the above-mentioned indicators, it is clear that the model achieved good indicators according to the results of the analysis, where the value of ($X^2/\text{degrees of freedom}$) 2019.794 which is greater than (5), and the value of P is significant.

Also, the index of the Goodness of fit Index (GFI = 0.842) is less than (0.9), in addition to the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI = 0.504), which is less than (0.9), as well as the Comparative Fit Index (CFI = 0.609), less than (0.9), the Normed Fit Index (NFI = 0.604), less than 0.9, and the Incremental Fit Index (IFI = 0.610), which is less than 0.9.

Accordingly, it should be noted that all the previous indicators confirm that all model estimates are significant, which shows that there is an indirect relationship between PsyCap and SS through OA; that is, OA plays the role of partial mediation between PsyCap and SS at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.

From the previous table, there is a significant effect of OA (mediating variable) on the relationship between PsyCap (independent variable) and SS (dependent variable).

According to the above-mentioned results, it was decided to reject the null hypothesis that said "there is no significant effect of OA a mediating variable of the relationship between PsyCap and SS at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt." The alternative hypothesis was accepted after it was found that there is a significant effect of PsyCap (independent variable) on SS (dependent variable) through the mediating variable (OA), that is, OA plays the mediating role on the relationship between PsyCap and SS. This decision was based on the value of the $X^2/\text{degrees of freedom}$, the value of P, the GFI, TLI, CFI, NFI, IFI.

10. Research Results

By reviewing the results of the descriptive analysis of the data on which the study was based and testing the hypotheses of the research, the study reached a set of results as follows:

1. Findings support the view that the dimensions of PsyCap (hope, optimism, resilience, and self-efficacy) were positively related to OA (optimization of opportunities and Search for New opportunities) at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The results are consistent with research conducted by Erkutlu, 2013; Gooty et al., 2009; Luthans & Youssef, 2007; and Avey et al., 2006.
2. The results support the view that PsyCap is positively related to SS (limited strategy, effective implementation, motivational culture, horizontal organization, transformational leadership, continuous innovation) at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The results are consistent with research conducted by Quisenberry, 2015; Nafei, 2015; Paek et al., 2015; Avey et al., 2014; Abdelwahab, 2013; Avey, et al., 2010, and Gooty et al, 2009.
3. The results support the view that OA is positively related to SS at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The results are consistent with research conducted by Tempelaar, 2010; Cao et al., 2010; Jansen et al., 2009; Han et al, 2001; and Wei et al., 2014.
4. There is a positive effect of OA as a mediating variable in explaining the effect of PsyCap on SS at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt; that is, OA plays the mediating role in the relationship between PsyCap and SS at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. There is an impact on PsyCap on SS through OA. The results are consistent with research conducted by Jurksiene & Pundziene, 2016; Chang & Hughes, 2012; Bouzari & Karatepe, 2017; Peng et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2012, and Zhao & Zhang 2010.

11. Recommendations

In the light of the previous results, the researcher concluded with a set of recommendations summarized as follows:

1. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt can help their employees, through training interventions, to develop their PsyCap.
2. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt should be careful in assigning relatively stressful tasks to those who are low on PsyCap as these individuals are more likely to report job stress.

3. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt should pay attention to building and strengthening the PsyCap of their workers. There are specific guidelines and numerous successful applications in the positive psychology literature for enhancing hope, optimism, resiliency, and self-efficacy.
4. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt can enhance the PsyCap in one's organization to improve performance and competitive advantage.
5. Managers can provide opportunities to build their own PsyCap and that of their associates through successful practice.
6. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt can invest in PsyCap by encouraging learning among employees. The more developed employees' positive psychological states become, the higher their PsyCap to draw from in dealing with the increasing demands and pressures of today's organizations.
7. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt should recognize that the level of an employees' PsyCap may play a role in leveraging what a positive organizational climate can contribute to OA and SS.
8. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt may look for employees who are high in terms of PsyCap. Not only has PsyCap been shown to be directly related to higher levels of performance and OA, but it is also logical that employees who are more hopeful, resilient, optimistic, and confident can provide higher values to an organization than can employees who are lower in these psychological capacities.
9. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt should take measures to increase employees' identification with their organization, such as striving for a higher organizational purpose. This might enhance employees' feeling that they are working for a higher good and higher moral standards.
10. The need to focus on the four dimensions of PsyCap and use them to increase OA among employees at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.
 - *As for hope*, it affects the attitudes of employees and then influences the feelings of OA and SS at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.
 - *As for resilience*, an individual's ability to adapt and be flexible may affect the level of OA at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.
 - *As for optimism*, the level of an individual affects the level of his ability to deal with adverse events in the work environment and then controls the feelings of OA at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.
 - *As for self-efficacy*, the decline in self-efficacy makes an individual contribute significantly to the increase OA at Teaching hospitals in Egypt.
11. The need to train managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt on how to develop the four dimensions of PsyCap through training courses targeting the spread of the spirit of hope and optimism among managers, and equipping them with skills to deal with different situations in order to ensure the achievement of positive feedback in the work environment.
12. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt must attend the development of the PsyCap as a competitive advantage that can actualize very important goals such as OA and SS.
13. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt can increase the level of PsyCap by using short training sessions of one to three-hour micro-interventions in which they measure PsyCap before and after the interventions.
14. Managers at Teaching hospitals in Egypt can increase PsyCap through Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations and Results (SOAR). Teaching Hospitals SOAR encourages their employees to work together to create a shared understanding of the status of the organizations and construct their future through dialogue and commitment to action.

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